

Neutronic Assessment about FeCrAl and SiC Claddings in SMART Nuclear Reactor

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ABSTRACT

In a world increasingly dependent on electricity, mitigating global warming and reducing environmental impact require a fundamental shift toward clean, reliable energy sources. This context presents favorable conditions to drive global research efforts to expand the role of nuclear power in the global energy matrix. Nuclear accidents, such as the Fukushima Daiichi accident, have shown that under extreme conditions, nuclear fuel can fail. The development of fuels and fuel-cladding materials that improve energy conversion efficiency in nuclear reactors and reduce the risk of damage in accident situations is therefore needed. This study, conducted at the Nuclear Engineering Department of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (DEN-UFMG), investigates the power density distribution and the infinity multiplication factor (k_{inf}) of the SMART Small Modular Reactor (SMR) when the claddings are changed by the ATFs' claddings, SiC, and also FeCrAl. The analysis was performed using the WIMSD-5B and PARCS codes. This work constitutes a phase of a broader research project focused on accident analysis and the evaluation of accident-tolerant fuels, and fuel-claddings (ATF) materials in SMRs through the coupling of neutronic and thermal-hydraulic codes. This multiphysics approach will provide insights into reactor kinetics, power and reactivity distribution, feedback effects, control and shutdown mechanisms, heat transfer, coolant flow dynamics, and overall safety performance. The preliminary results obtained are in agreement with the reference data from the Nuclear Characteristics Analysis Report for the System-integrated Modular Advanced Reactor (KAERI/TR-1162/98), supporting the project's continuity.

Keywords: Small Modular Reactor (SMR), Accident Tolerant Fuels (ATF), SMART Reactor, Neutronic Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The need to accelerate the deployment of nuclear energy in order to meet climate change targets was highlighted in the first Global Stocktake under the Paris Agreement at the 2023 United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP28) in Dubai, United Arab Emirates, where more than 20 countries committed to tripling global nuclear energy capacity by 2050. According to the IAEA's 2024 document, "Small Modular Reactors: Advances in SMR Developments," nuclear energy is a source of low-carbon electricity, heat, and hydrogen generation with the highest power density, thereby playing a key role in meeting energy security and sustainable development goals.

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are advanced nuclear systems designed to generate up to 300 MW(e) of baseload, controlled, and on-demand electricity through compact, factory-fabricated modules that can be easily transported and installed. According to the IAEA's Advanced Reactor Information System (ARIS) [1], global interest in SMRs is rapidly expanding, with operational units and numerous projects under development worldwide. These plants are equipped with enhanced safety features and designed to be deployed as single- or multi-module plants, reducing installation time and benefiting from economies of scale through serial production. Due to their smaller footprint and adaptable siting, SMRs are particularly well-suited for remote areas, small electrical grids, and industrial or regional energy clusters, making them an appealing option for countries that

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are beginning to adopt nuclear power [1].

Given the growing global interest in Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) as flexible, safe, and scalable sources of clean energy, accurate simulation of their performance under both normal and transient conditions is essential to ensure their reliability and efficiency.

Among these advanced systems, the System-integrated Modular Advanced Reactor (SMART), developed by the Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute (KAERI), stands out as a 110 MW(e) integral pressurized water reactor designed with compact modularity and enhanced safety. The SMART core uses UO_2 fuel enriched to 4.95 w/o U-235. The cladding is Zircaloy, a material traditionally employed in light water reactors (LWRs) due to its well-known behavior and good neutron economy. However, as revealed by the Fukushima-Daiichi accident, Zircaloy's vulnerability to high-temperature oxidation in contact with steam during transient events, such as prolonged station blackouts, poses a major safety concern [2].

Concepts currently under consideration include modifying the existing Zr alloy cladding through surface treatment applying a coating or replacing the cladding material entirely. Each concept varies in the extent of the potential improvement in accident tolerance and the time and cost required to develop and demonstrate the new concept through licensing its use in reactors [2].

Therefore, simulating SMART reactor operation not only allows evaluation of its thermal-hydraulic and neutronic behavior but also enables assessment of alternative, accident-tolerant cladding materials, such as FeCrAl alloys and silicon carbide (SiC), which exhibit superior oxidation resistance and structural stability under extreme conditions. These studies are essential to improving the overall safety, performance, and resilience of next-generation SMRs.

This study, conducted at the Nuclear Engineering Department of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (DEN-UFGM), investigates the power density distribution and the infinity multiplication factor (k_{inf}) of the SMART reactor when the claddings are changed by the ATFs claddings SiC and also FeCrAl. The analysis was conducted using the WIMSD-5B code and PARCS code [7, 8].

This work constitutes a phase of a broader research project focused on accident analysis and the evaluation of Accident-Tolerant Fuels and Fuel Claddings (ATF) materials in SMRs through the coupling of neutronic and thermal-hydraulic codes. This multiphysics approach will provide insights into reactor kinetics, power and reactivity distribution, feedback effects, control and shutdown mechanisms, heat transfer, coolant flow dynamics, and overall safety performance, enabling a deeper parameter analysis of the new ATFs.

2. AIMS AND METHODOLOGY

This study analyzes the neutronic behavior of the SMART reactor at the Beginning of Cycle (BOC), Hot Full Power (HFP) and All Rods Out (ARO) conditions using the PARCS simulation code. The analysis compares the reactor's response when its standard fuel cladding is replaced with two Accident Tolerant Fuel Claddings (ATF): SiC and FeCrAl.

The SMART reactor, conceptually developed by the Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute (KAERI), is a small, advanced integral PWR that produces 110 MW(e) at full power [3]. The reactor design enabled the pressure vessel to enclose all primary system components, including steam generators, main cooling pumps, and pressurizers. This allows for modular reactor design and a passive safety system by eliminating cooling circuits, for example.

The reactor core consists of 57 fuel assemblies arranged in 4 different rod combinations: A, B, C, and D. The fuel rods contain UO_2 enriched to 4.95 w/o U-235. The boron control rod is composed of Al_2O_3 - B_4C being 4% B_4C [4] with B-10 enriched to 30 w/o admixed in an Al_2O_3 matrix. The gadolinium fuel rods are composed of 12% Gd_2O_3 (natural Gd) mixed in UO_2 enriched to 1.8 w/o U-235 [3]. Fig. 1 shows the core loading pattern as well as the burnable poison rod arrangement in assemblies of the SMART reactor:

Figure I. Core Loading Pattern and burnable poison rod arrangement of the SMART nuclear reactor [3]

2.1. The Advanced Fe Alloy Cladding Austenitic Stainless Steel

Advanced Fe Alloy Cladding Austenitic Stainless Steel was used as cladding material in the early days of LWR deployment. Cladding failures due to stress-corrosion cracking, especially in the highly oxidizing water chemistries of boiling water reactors (BWRs), combined with higher neutron absorption than Zr alloys, led to the phasing out of steel use by the early 1980s. However, significant progress has been made recently in evaluating the use of ferritic FeCrAl alloys as potential cladding materials, where the high-temperature oxidation resistance in steam relies on the formation of an alumina scale [5].

Oxidation resistance in these alloys has been shown to extend up to around 1750 K, close to their melting point [5]. The main issue with Fe alloy cladding is its higher neutron capture cross-section compared to Zr alloys, which would require either increased fuel enrichment or reduced cladding thickness to compensate for the neutron penalty. [4]

2.2. Silicon Carbide Composite Cladding Hi-Nicalon type S (SiC HNS):

The Silicon Carbide Composite Cladding HNS, a Hi-Nicalon type S fibers embedded in a monolithic SiC matrix, has been identified as a potential candidate for cladding in advanced nuclear reactors due to its high elasticity, oxidation resistance, and deformation resistance. Monolithic silicon carbide has shown excellent mechanical performance in high-temperature environments, irradiation resistance, and steam oxidation resistance at temperatures up to 1600°C [5]. However, its inherent fragile nature limits its application. Recently, high-purity, high-quality SiC fiber-reinforced composites have been developed to address this limitation.

The use of SiC HNS as a new cladding material can also affect fuel rod and fuel assembly designs. In economic terms, SiC has lower neutron absorption than other candidate coatings, potentially resulting in savings [5]. Table I shows the percentage, in mass, for Zircaloy 4, SiC HNS and the FeCrAl Alloys: C06M, C035M, C36M and C36MK. The SiC HNS and the FeCrAl alloys were used to replace the Zircaloy.

Table I. Claddings Compositions.

Element	Zircaloy	SiC HNS	Cladding			
			C06M	C35M	C36M	C36MK
Mass (%)						
Al			6.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
C		30.90				
Cr	0.10		10.00	13.00	13.00	21.00
Fe	0.21		81.75	79.75	78.75	71.00
Hf	0.01					
Mo			2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00
O		0.20				
Si		68.90	0.20	0.20	0.20	
Sn	1.45					
Y			0.05	0.05	0.05	
Zr	98.23					

2.3. Codes and Nuclear Data

The Purdue Advanced Reactor Core Simulator (PARCS) is a three-dimensional (3D) reactor core simulator that solves the steady-state and time-dependent, multigroup neutron diffusion and low-order transport equations in orthogonal and non-orthogonal geometries. PARCS is available as a standalone code for performing calculations or can be coupled directly to the thermal-hydraulics system code RELAP5 via the PVM message-passing interface [7].

The WIMSD-5B is a widely used deterministic transport code for reactor physics calculations, particularly for lattice-cell analysis in thermal reactors, and it is available via OECD/NEA [8]. It was used to compute multi-group cross sections for the PARCS code. WIMSD-5B code allows the homogenization of materials in different concentric annuli within a circular cell, as in the case of this work. Figure 2.a shows the collapsed geometry where all the fuel assembly materials (fuel, burnable poisons, gap, clad, and moderator) are homogenized in concentric annuli. In this geometry, the fuel (UO_2) and the burnable poisons ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-B}_4\text{C}$ and $\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_3\text{-UO}_2$), are homogenized in a single annulus. In Figure 2.b, the collapsed geometry was organized in a way that the fuel-burnable poison annulus, from Figure 2.a, was divided into four fuel annuli interspersed by four homogenized burnable poison annuli. Figure 2.c represents a Cluster problem geometry in which all fuel assembly rods were considered. All rods, represented by the small circles, are immersed in an equivalent moderator fluid area. All geometries are examples from the fuel assembly D and maintain the V_M/V_F ratio (moderator volume/fuel volume).

Figure 2. a) Collapsed geometry; b) Collapsed geometry with four interspersed fuel-burning poison annuli; c) Cluster problem (obtained from the WIMSB-5D output).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Radial and Axial Power Distribution

The obtained cross sections, considering the geometry shown in Figure 2.b, were selected to feed the PARCS code because they provided radial and axial power distributions under BOC and ARO conditions that were in better agreement with the KAERI document [3]. The axial and radial power distribution comparisons, along with the relative error between the PARCS calculation and the KAERI data, are shown in Figures 3a and 3b. The average error in the power density distribution, by assembly, at BOC, HFP, and ARO, was around 11%. The obtained k_{inf} , provided by PARCS from the nuclear reactor core, was 1.0582.

Figure 3. a) Assemblywise radial power distribution comparison between the PARCS output (1 LINE), the KAERI/TR-1162/98 data (2 LINE), both using Zircaloy cladding, and their relative error. 3. b) Core average axial power distribution comparison in BOC, HZP, and ARO between (KAERI/TR-1162/98) in a red dashed line and the PARCS output in a blue continuous line (both for Zircaloy cladding) and their relative error in each specified point at the core height.

3.2. k_{inf} Values Calculated by WIMSD-5B

In the next step, the WIMSD-5B code was used to calculate the k_{inf} values considering also the proposed ATFs claddings replacing Zircaloy. The values obtained when SiC HNS was used as cladding for type A, B, C, and D fuel assemblies, as shown in Table II, are in good agreement with those obtained using Zircaloy as fuel cladding. The k_{inf} values obtained by the FeCrAl alloys, when tested as fuel claddings, were lower. The table presents k_{inf} values from the SMART fuel assemblies A, B, C, and D for Zircaloy, FeCrAl Alloys, and SiC cladding materials, at BOC, HFP, and ARO conditions. The geometry and cladding dimensions were the same as proposed by the KAERI document for Zircaloy cladding.

The FeCrAl Alloy, which presented the best k_{inf} was the C06M. From now on, this alloy will be used in the next steps. To achieve criticality, preserving the fuel rod geometry, the fuel enrichment was gradually increased. In Table III, k_{inf} values are presented for different U-235 fuel enrichments ranging from 4.95% to 15%.

Table II. k_{inf} values from the SMART fuel assemblies for different cladding materials.

Fuel Assembly	A	B	C	D
k_{inf}				
Clad Materials				
Zircaloy	1.138019	1.150293	1.080500	1.058839
SiC	1.142153	1.154274	1.086235	1.066009
FeCrAl C06M	0.839608	0.848661	0.799810	0.785601
FeCrAl C35M	0.837447	0.848661	0.797738	0.783562
FeCrAl C36M	0.837466	0.846504	0.797751	0.783573
FeCrAl C36MK	0.832871	0.841883	0.793281	0.779131

 Table III. k_{inf} values for C06M alloy and different enrichments (w/o)

Fuel Assembly	A	B	C	D
k_{inf}				
Enrichment (w/o)				
4.95%	0.883961	0.848661	0.799810	0.785601
7.00%	0.929608	0.936954	0.898021	0.886245
9.00%	0.991447	0.997506	0.967157	0.957517
11.00%	1.039457	1.044559	1.020771	1.012851
13.00%	1.078706	1.083090	1.064332	1.057777
15.00%	1.111995	1.115828	1.100957	1.095481

3.3. PARCS Code Results

Cross-sections data obtained by the WIMSD-5B code were fed in the PARCS modelling. This simulation was performed to determine the relative axial and radial power distribution and k_{inf} values of the SMART reactor core. Three PARCS outputs were obtained to analyze three different cladding materials: Zircaloy (4,95% enrichment fuel), SiC (4,95% enrichment fuel), and FeCrAl C06M (15% enrichment fuel). These outputs were then compared against the standard radial power distribution provided by the KAERI document.

Figures 5 and 6 show, respectively, the resulting SMART radial and axial core power distribution values. Figure 5 presents four radial power distributions from different cladding materials, with numerical data from each fuel assembly and a color scale ranging from green to red, representing lower to higher relative power values. Figure 5.a. is the standard data from the KAERI document, using Zircaloy as cladding. The Figure 5.b. corresponds to the PARCS output using Zircaloy as cladding. Figure 5.c. represents the PARCS output using SiC cladding, and in Figure 5d. shows a PARCS output using FeCrAl C06M alloy. The results in Figure 5 show that the neutronic behavior of the ATF claddings is in good agreement with that of the Zircaloy reference. The comparison between Zircaloy and SiC cladding, in particular, indicates a high degree of similarity, with an average error of 0.345% for power distribution and 0.472% for k_{inf} core.

The FeCrAl C06M analysis is more complex, as its higher neutron absorption required the fuel enrichment to be increased from 4.95% to 15%. This enrichment change, in turn, lessens the impact of the burnable absorbers on the radial power distribution. Consequently, the radial cosine profile becomes less flat, with a higher power peak and lower peripheral values. This behavior would need to be compensated for by redesigning the burnable poison rods (e.g., using a higher B₄C or Gadolinium content), which will be the subject of future study. The average error between the Zircaloy and FeCrAl C06M power distribution and core k_{inf} is, respectively, 7.473% and 0.231%.

Figure 5. Radial power distribution for different types of claddings: a)KAERI Zircaloy; b)PARCS Zircaloy; c)PARCS SiC; d) PARCS FeCrAl C06M alloy.

Figure 6 shows the cosine profile behavior from the Core Average Axial Power Distribution Comparison between four different cladding materials. In a blue continuous line, the KAERI document data cladding by Zircaloy; in an orange line, the PARCS output cladding by Zircaloy; in a grey line, the PARCS output cladding by SiC; and in a yellow line, the PARCS output cladding by the FeCrAl C06M alloy. The axial power distribution behavior remains unchanged when only the cladding material is altered, and the reactor geometry is maintained for all simulations.

Figure 6. Core average axial power distribution comparison in BOC, HZP, and ARO in the SMART reactor

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study performed a neutronic assessment of the SMART SMR core, evaluating the performance behavior of replacing the reference Zircaloy cladding with the ATF candidates: SiC HNS and the FeCrAl C06M alloy. The analysis was conducted using a coupled WIMSD-5B and PARCS code package, and the baseline neutronic model was successfully verified against reference data from the KAERI/TR-1162/98 report, confirming the accuracy of the simulation methodology.

The results demonstrate two distinct pathways for ATF implementation. The SiC HNS cladding proved to be an excellent neutronic equivalent to Zircaloy. The core k_{int} and radial power distributions were highly similar to those of the reference case, suggesting that SiC HNS could potentially serve as a "drop-in" replacement, offering enhanced accident resilience with minimal penalty to the core's neutron economy or operational parameters.

Conversely, the FeCrAl C06M cladding introduces a more complex engineering replacement. Its significant neutron-absorption penalty required a substantial increase in fuel enrichment from 4.95% to 15% to achieve criticality, as in Zircaloy-cladding designs. While this compensation was effective, it fundamentally altered the core physics, diminishing the relative impact of the burnable absorbers. This resulted in a less desirable radial power profile, characterized by a more pronounced central power peak and lower peripheral values. This finding is critical, as it confirms that FeCrAl cannot be considered a simple "drop-in" replacement and would necessitate a comprehensive redesign of the core, particularly the burnable poison management.

Although the results presented are preliminary, the data's coherence supports the continuity of this research. The immediate next step for the FeCrAl analysis will be to investigate redesigns of the burnable absorber rods, such as modifying the B4C or Gadolinia concentrations, to suppress the observed power peak and flatten the radial profile. More broadly, this validated neutronic model serves as the foundational phase for the project's ultimate goal: coupling the PARCS code with a thermal-hydraulic system code. This future approach is essential for moving beyond steady-state analysis and evaluating the true safety and performance benefits of SiC and FeCrAl claddings under transient and accident conditions.

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